

A Methodological Development of an Eigenmode-Based Monte Carlo Approach for Uncertainty Quantification of Power Distribution in High-Dominance-Ratio Systems

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803498

ABSTRACT

Accurate uncertainty quantification (UQ) is essential for reactor design and safety assessment. Monte Carlo (MC) methods, thanks to their intrinsic physical fidelity, provide an ideal framework for this purpose. However, sampling-based UQ approaches rapidly become computationally prohibitive, motivating the use of sensitivity-based techniques. In this context, the Collision History (CH) method has emerged as an effective Generalised Perturbation Theory implementation, enabling the estimation of sensitivity coefficients for any perturbable parameter within a single MC simulation. These coefficients allow the efficient propagation of uncertainties in nuclear data, material properties, and operating conditions to virtually any response function of interest. Despite its efficiency, CH faces practical limitations when applied to large or high-dominance-ratio systems, where the convergence of crucial quantities—such as the power distribution—becomes excessively slow. This work introduces a new methodology that addresses this issue by combining CH with an eigenmode-based expansion of the fission source. The method has been implemented and verified in a purpose-built Python MC code, demonstrating its feasibility and correctness on simplified reactor configurations. The paper also discusses future developments, including the application of the methodology to more realistic 2D/3D reactor systems and its extension to coupled neutronic-thermal-hydraulic analyses, ultimately enabling comprehensive multiphysics UQ for advanced reactor concepts.

Keywords: eigenmodes, Monte Carlo, Perturbation Theory, Uncertainty Quantification

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate and reliable uncertainty quantification (UQ) is essential for the design and safety assessment of Advanced Nuclear Reactors (ANRs), whose innovative configurations and limited operational experience introduce larger uncertainties in data, geometry, and material properties compared to conventional systems [1]. Among the various UQ strategies, sampling-based approaches—such as the Total Monte Carlo (TMC) method—aim to propagate uncertainties by repeatedly sampling input parameters. However, these techniques remain computationally prohibitive, as they require thousands of independent reactor calculations to span the full uncertainty range of the inputs [2]. When the number of uncertain parameters increases, a more efficient alternative to sampling-based approaches is offered by the *sandwich rule* [3]:

$$\text{Var}[R] = (S_x^R)^\top \text{Cov}[x] S_x^R$$

where $\text{Cov}[x]$ is the covariance matrix of the uncertain parameters. The key quantity is the sensitivity coefficient, $S_x^R = \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x}\right) \frac{x}{R}$, which expresses the relative change in the response with respect to a relative change in the input parameter. These coefficients constitute the fundamental metrics required for sensitivity-based analyses, whose general goal is to quantify how input variations affect model responses. These coefficients are widely used for design optimisation, parameter screening, and, as in the present work, they are employed specifically for efficient UQ.

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Several strategies exist to evaluate sensitivity coefficients. Finite-difference perturbations provide a straightforward but computationally expensive option, as each parameter requires additional high-statistics simulations. Perturbation-theory-based methods offer a more efficient alternative, estimating the variation of a response without explicitly simulating perturbed systems [3]. In particular, Generalised Perturbation Theory (GPT) provides a linear framework that combines forward and adjoint information to evaluate sensitivities [4].

Monte Carlo (MC) neutron-transport methods are widely used for high-fidelity reactor analysis due to their physical accuracy and ability to handle complex geometries without phase-space discretisation. Within this framework, GPT—originally developed for deterministic transport—has been successfully extended to MC methods [4]. Among recent GPT implementations, the Collision History (CH) technique [5] has shown excellent efficiency. It extends the concept of importance to MC calculations by propagating information through successive neutron generations—the so-called latent generations—and enables the simultaneous estimation of sensitivities for virtually any linear or bilinear response, allowing all perturbable parameters to be treated within a single simulation. The Iterated Fission Matrix (IFM) [6] method similarly exploits information transferred across latent generations and allows accurate reconstruction of higher-order eigenmodes while requiring significantly coarser spatial discretisation than the traditional Fission Matrix approach.

Despite these advances, CH-based methods face practical difficulties in systems characterised by a high dominance ratio, i.e., when the ratio between the fundamental and the first higher fission eigenvalue approaches unity ($k_1/k_0 \approx 1$) [7, 8, 9]. In such cases, the convergence of local sensitivities—such as those of the power distribution—becomes extremely slow, often requiring hundreds of latent generations [10]. Moreover, increasing the number of latent generations amplifies the statistical noise of the sensitivity estimators [7]. This limitation is particularly critical since the power distribution is not only essential for reliable criticality calculations but is also directly tied to reactor safety margins.

The objective of this work is to present a methodology that improves the stability and convergence of sensitivity estimations for power distribution in high-dominance-ratio systems. The proposed approach combines the CH method with the IFM formulation and an eigenmode-based expansion of the fission source, enhancing eigenvalue separation and enabling the efficient estimation of the sensitivity of the power distribution. Although the present study focuses on neutronics, the methodology represents a first step toward extending MC-based UQ to multiphysics environments, where uncertainties arising from different physical domains—such as thermal-hydraulics—must be consistently propagated.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 presents the theoretical formulation of the CH-IFM-eigenmode approach, while Section 3 describes its implementation in a purpose-built Monte Carlo prototype. Verification and preliminary numerical results are reported in Section 4, and future developments together with final remarks are discussed in Section 5.

2. THEORETICAL FORMULATION

This section briefly introduces the essential concepts of the CH and IFM methods, outlining the key ideas needed to understand the efficiency of the proposed framework. For comprehensive descriptions, the reader is referred to Refs. [5, 6].

2.1. Collision History method

The CH approach is based on the concepts of *rejected events* and *collision history*. Perturbed parameters x (e.g., microscopic cross sections, average neutron yield, scattering laws) are interpreted as probability distributions governing physical events such as collisions, emission energies, or scattering angles. Artificially introducing a perturbation biases these probability densities and therefore alters the underlying sampling process. To restore physically consistent neutron transport, a rejection mechanism is applied: biased events are accepted or discarded according to the imposed perturbation. Both accepted and re-

jected events are stored in the particle's collision history, which is inherited by all its descendants and later used to estimate the effect of the perturbation on the chosen response. Rather than generating new particle tracks, each neutron follows the reference trajectory and its statistical weight is adjusted according to accepted and rejected events in its history. When applied to the full neutron population, this preserves the unperturbed phase-space distributions and yields an unbiased estimator of the perturbed response.

2.2. Iterated Fission Matrix method

The IFM approach extends the traditional FM method by enabling the calculation of higher forward and adjoint eigenmodes of the l -th iterated fission kernel $({}^l)F(\mathbf{r}' \leftarrow \mathbf{r})$. The kernel represents the expected number of neutron descendants born in position \mathbf{r}' after l generations from a neutron initially born in \mathbf{r} . After spatial discretisation of the domain, the continuous kernel $({}^l)F(\mathbf{r}' \leftarrow \mathbf{r})$ is reduced to the discretised matrix $({}^l)\bar{\bar{F}}$, and the eigenvalue problem can be expressed as in the standard FM formulation [6]:

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}}_i = \left(\frac{1}{k_i}\right)^l ({}^l)\bar{\bar{F}} \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i \quad \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^\dagger = \left(\frac{1}{k_i}\right)^l ({}^l)\bar{\bar{F}}^T \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^\dagger \quad (1)$$

where $\{(k_i)^l, \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i, \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^\dagger\}$ form the i -th eigentriplet of the discretised l -th iterated eigenproblem. IFM improves the estimation of higher-order eigenvalues and eigenvectors by approximating an iterated fission operator that is spatially smoother and exhibits an increased spectral separation of the physically relevant modes, thereby reducing discretisation-induced contamination of subdominant eigenmodes.

Within the collision history-based framework, the effect of a perturbation in a physical parameter x (e.g., a cross section or resonance parameter) on the $({}^l)F_{I \leftarrow J}$ element of the discretised fission kernel can be evaluated from the average number of accepted and rejected collisions of type x in the histories of particles that induce fission in spatial cell I and whose l -th ancestor was born in cell J . The corresponding estimator can be expressed as [11]:

$$\frac{d({}^l)F_{I \leftarrow J}}{dx} = \frac{\sum_{p \in \alpha} w_p \delta(I_p) \delta(J_{l^{\text{th}} \text{ ancestor of } p}) \sum_{g=\alpha-l}^{\alpha} (\text{ACC}_x - \text{REJ}_x)}{\sum_{s \in \alpha-l} w_s \delta(\text{cell}_s, J)} \quad (2)$$

where α denotes the current generation at which the fission in I is recorded. In the numerator, the difference between accepted and rejected events $(\text{ACC}_x - \text{REJ}_x)$ quantifies the cumulative effect of the perturbation x over the latent generations connecting J and I , and $\delta(\cdot)$ denotes a discrete indicator (Kronecker-like) function selecting events occurring in the considered spatial cell (I or J) for the neutron p (or its l -th ancestor). The weighting factors w_p and w_s correspond to the statistical weights of the particles at the present and ancestor generations, respectively. This formulation establishes the link between the CH formalism and the IFM framework, providing the quantity required to compute the derivative of the iterated fission matrix with respect to any physical parameter of interest.

2.3. Eigenmode expansion of the perturbed fission source

The truncated IFM eigenvalue expansion provides a convenient set of biorthogonal bases for projecting the response of the fission source to perturbations. The effect of a perturbation in a given parameter x on the n -th eigenmode of the fission source can be expressed as [12]:

$$\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{S}}_n}{dx} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i \frac{\bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^{\dagger T} \left(\frac{d({}^l)\bar{\bar{F}}}{dx}\right) \bar{\mathbf{S}}_n}{\lambda_n - \lambda_i} \quad (3)$$

where λ_i and λ_n (i.e., $\lambda_i = (k_i)^l$) are the eigenvalues associated with the i -th and n -th modes, respectively, and $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_i, \bar{\mathbf{S}}_i^\dagger$ are the corresponding right and left eigenvectors of the discretised iterated fission matrix ${}^{(l)}\bar{\mathbf{F}}$.

In the fundamental case ($n = 0$), Eq. (3) gives the coefficients of the linear expansion describing the perturbation of the fission source, which in a critical system is directly proportional to the power distribution. Evaluating its sensitivity is therefore central to propagating uncertainties to reactor observables. The coefficient corresponding to $i = n$ is undefined and is fixed by enforcing the normalisation of the total fission source, ensuring a constrained neutron production rate. Each term in the expansion is weighted by the spectral separation $\lambda_n - \lambda_i$, which controls the contribution of each eigenmode: modes associated with smaller eigenvalues contribute weakly and allow the series to be truncated.

Localised perturbations may require more modes, but the IFM formulation improves the projection in two ways. First, it provides more accurate estimates of higher-order eigenvalues for a given mesh, reducing discretisation errors in the terms $1/(k_n - k_i)$. Second, using the l -th iterated fission kernel ${}^{(l)}\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ increases spectral separation, since $\lambda_i = (k_i)^l$. As a result, $(k_n)^l - (k_i)^l$ is larger than $(k_n - k_i)$ for any i and $l > 0$, which reduces the statistical uncertainty of the projection coefficients and improves the stability of the expansion.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

A lightweight MC prototype has been developed in Python to test and verify the proposed methodology. Although not intended to match production codes, the tool is transparent and easily modifiable, making it well suited for methodological development. Neutrons are tracked in full 3D, while tallies are restricted to one spatial coordinate, effectively modelling a slab geometry composed of user-defined material layers. The high configurability allows localised perturbations of nuclear data in selected regions of the domain. The code implements the main neutron interactions—capture, scattering (including S_1 anisotropy), and fission—and records the corresponding reaction rates and flux. A multigroup energy structure is adopted, with cross sections homogenised and collapsed from SERPENT 2. Both CH and IFM are natively integrated, enabling perturbations of macroscopic fission, capture, and scattering cross sections, as well as the average neutron yield. Beyond sensitivity coefficients, CH provides the derivative of the (iterated) fission matrix, which—together with the eigentriplets—allows the computation of the perturbed fission source via the truncated eigenmode expansion of Eq. (3). The core functionalities of the prototype have been benchmarked against SERPENT 2, showing agreement in reaction rates, flux, and CH-based sensitivity coefficients. The eigenmode projection procedure has also been validated through direct perturbation tests within the same framework, confirming the internal consistency of the implementation.

4. VERIFICATION AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

At the current stage, the in-house MC code has reached a stable level of development. Verification was performed on a simplified PWR fuel-rod configuration consisting of a 200 cm fuel column with helium gap and Zircaloy cladding, axially bounded by 20 cm of light-water moderator above and below. The verification campaign began with the assessment of fundamental MC tallies—reaction rates, flux, and neutron balance. Figure 1 shows the comparison with SERPENT 2 for the neutron flux and the effective multiplication factor, confirming the correct behaviour of the prototype code. The maximum relative standard deviation of the Monte Carlo neutron flux estimator for energy groups 1 to 4 is, respectively, 11.3%, 14.0%, 12.4%, and 9.8%.

As a first step, the correct implementation of the CH method was verified by computing the sensitivity of the effective multiplication factor. Sensitivities to perturbations of scattering, fission, capture, and average neutron yield were evaluated using CH and benchmarked against SERPENT 2, showing

Figure 1. Neutron flux verification against Serpent results

consistent agreement. Figure 2(a) reports the results for the perturbation of the macroscopic fission cross section. The IFM implementation was first verified by considering a single ancestor generation, which corresponds to the conventional FM method and reproduces the fission kernel (Figure 2(b)). Its improved efficiency relative to FM was then assessed by varying the spatial mesh. As shown in Figure 2(c), IFM achieves the same accuracy in estimating the dominance ratio—correctly capturing both the fundamental and first higher eigenvalues—while requiring significantly coarser spatial discretisation. This reduces the need for fine meshes and lowers the overall computational cost.

Figure 2. Verification of in-house MC code capability for computation of (a) sensitivity coefficient, (b) fission matrix, (c) Iterated Fission Matrix with different number of latent generations

The eigenmode-based perturbation of the fission source has been implemented and tested for perturbations of macroscopic fission and capture cross sections. Verification has been performed against a direct perturbation benchmark, used here as reference. For compactness, only the case of a perturbation applied to the fourth (thermal) energy group capture cross-section is reported. Two spatial configurations were analysed: (i) a perturbation applied to the outer quarter of the multiplying region, and (ii) a perturbation applied to the central half of the multiplying region. For each configuration, the direct benchmark was obtained by performing two perturbed simulations with $\pm 5\%$ variation of the corresponding macroscopic cross section, together with a reference one (unperturbed system). The IFM was used to extract the fundamental modes of both the unperturbed and perturbed configurations (see Fig-

ure 3(a) and Figure 4(a)), although the forward fundamental mode could also be obtained directly from MC tallies. These modes were then employed to compute the centred finite-difference estimate of the variation of the fission source.

In contrast, the proposed methodology enables the evaluation of the first-order (linear) perturbation term $d\bar{S}_0/dx$ within a single simulation by combining the CH and IFM methods. The IFM tallies provide the eigentriplets $\{\lambda_i, \bar{S}_i, \bar{S}_i^\dagger\}$ of the reference configuration— analogously to the direct-perturbation benchmark— while the CH tallies supply the derivative of the IFM, $d^{(l)}\bar{F}/dx$. These quantities are then combined through Eq. (3) to compute both the variation of the fundamental fission source and the associated sensitivity coefficient, $S_x^{S_0} = \frac{d\bar{S}_0}{dx} \frac{x}{\bar{S}_0}$. It is important to note that the fission-source perturbation is obtained entirely in post-processing. This is enabled by the CH formalism, which biases the sampling of collision events while restoring the correct transport through the rejection mechanism. Consequently, the neutron population evolves according to the unperturbed physics, allowing both the eigentriplets of the reference system and the CH tallies (dF/dx) to be extracted from a single simulation, where multiple perturbations can be treated simultaneously.

Figure 3. Benchmark for perturbation of the fourth-group capture cross section applied to the outer quarter of the multiplying region.

Figure 4. Benchmark for perturbation of the fourth-group capture cross section applied to the central half of the multiplying region.

Figures 3–4 compare the eigenmode perturbation theory prediction with the direct-perturbation benchmark. In both spatial configurations, the method accurately reproduces the variation of the fission source once a sufficient number of projection bases is included. As expected from the structure of the expansion, the contribution of each eigenmode to the perturbed source is determined by the combined effect of its projection coefficient α_j and its spectral separation $(\lambda_0 - \lambda_j)$. As a result, the number of modes required to accurately reconstruct the perturbation cannot be fixed a priori, since it depends on the relative balance between these two factors (see Tables I and II). In the central symmetric perturbation, the induced response preserves even parity: only symmetric eigenmodes are excited, while

Mode	α_j	$\lambda_0 - \lambda_j$	$\alpha_j / (\lambda_0 - \lambda_j)$
1	0.0541	0.0238	2.2712
2	-0.0541	0.0614	-0.8814
3	0.0362	0.1104	0.3277
4	0.0104	0.1674	0.0624
5	0.0111	0.2298	0.0481
6	-0.0201	0.2944	-0.0682
7	-0.0157	0.3590	-0.0437
8	-0.0037	0.4215	-0.0088
9	0.0076	0.4811	0.0158

Table I. Projection coefficients and spectral separation for the outer quarter perturbed configuration.

Mode	α_j	$\lambda_0 - \lambda_j$	$\alpha_j / (\lambda_0 - \lambda_j)$
1	0.0004	0.0238	0.0164
2	0.1083	0.0614	1.7638
3	0.0004	0.1104	0.0033
4	-0.0213	0.1674	-0.1270
5	0.0000	0.2298	0.0001
6	0.0403	0.2944	0.1370
7	0.0001	0.3590	0.0002
8	0.0072	0.4215	0.0170
9	-0.0003	0.4811	-0.0005

Table II. Projection coefficients and spectral separation for the central half perturbed configuration.

antisymmetric (odd) modes remain orthogonal to the forcing term. In the continuous symmetric limit this implies $\alpha_{2k+1} = \bar{\mathbf{S}}_{2k+1}^\dagger \left(\frac{d^{(l)} \bar{\mathbf{F}}}{dx} \right) \bar{\mathbf{S}}_0 = 0$. Numerically, odd-mode coefficients are two to three orders of magnitude smaller than the even ones (Table II), due to statistical noise and slight symmetry breaking in the discretised operators, and their contribution is negligible. Accordingly, using 2, 4, or more symmetric modes yields identical reconstructed shapes (Figure 4(b,c)), consistently with the eigenmode physics where a symmetric forcing cannot excite antisymmetric modes and higher-order modes contribute progressively less.

A major advantage of the proposed method lies in its computational efficiency. While a centred finite-difference approach requires one reference simulation plus two additional runs per perturbed parameter, the CH-IFM-eigenmode method provides all sensitivities from a single simulation, with only a modest overhead due to CH tallies. In the present study, direct perturbation required two additional simulations per parameter, whereas a single CH run incurred only a modest computational-time overhead (about 7%) while providing sensitivity information for all parameters simultaneously, resulting in a substantial reduction of the overall computational cost for power-distribution sensitivity analyses.

5. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS AND CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a new methodology for uncertainty quantification in Monte Carlo simulations, combining the Collision History and Iterated Fission Matrix methods with an eigenmode-based expansion to efficiently estimate the sensitivity of the power distribution to any perturbable parameter. The formulation was implemented and verified in a self-developed MC framework, specifically designed for methodological testing, and successfully benchmarked against SERPENT for a representative PWR pin-cell configuration. The methodology demonstrated that the sensitivity of power distribution to any perturbable parameter can be evaluated with a single simulation, confirming the validity of the approach and significantly improving computational efficiency.

Future developments will focus on extending the methodology to realistic 2D and 3D reactor configurations. Key steps include the development of a dedicated estimator for Eq. (3) that directly evaluates the numerator in a single pass, improving computational efficiency, and the adoption of Petrov-Galerkin projection techniques to enable scalable IFM-based analyses in large systems. Such configurations are expected to most clearly highlight the performance gains of the proposed CH-IFM-eigenmode approach, particularly in the convergence behaviour of power-distribution sensitivities in high-dominance-ratio systems. Dedicated studies will also be carried out to quantify the number of latent generations required to achieve stable sensitivity estimators in these scenarios.

In parallel, the coupling of the neutronic solver with a thermal-hydraulic domain (e.g., via OpenFOAM) will enable the propagation of uncertainties associated with temperature, density, and feedback-driven

effects, thus extending the framework to full multiphysics UQ.

Once these developments are completed and the capability to simulate full-scale systems is achieved, the methodology will be tested against established benchmark problems, paving the way for its application to advanced reactor concepts and its use as a robust tool for high-fidelity multiphysics uncertainty quantification.

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